

Metal Complexes of some Peptide Derivatives. Part-VIII. Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Zinc(II) with some Salicyloylamino Acids

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pH-metric study on the complexation equilibria of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} (M^{2+}) with some salicyloylamino acids, $(o)\text{HO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(=\text{O})\text{NHCH}(\text{R})\text{COOH}$ or (H_sL), where $\text{R}=\text{H}$ (salicyloyl glycine), CH_3 (salicyloyl dl- α -alanine), $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SCH}_3$ (salicyloyl dl-methionine), provided evidence of formation of ML , ML_2^- and $\text{ML}(\text{OH})^-$ complexes through bidentate ($\text{O},\bar{\text{O}}$) chelation by the amide carbonyl oxygen atom and phenolate oxygen atom of the ligand, leaving the carboxylate group uncoordinated in these complexes. Formation constants at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium and ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaNO_3) were in the order, $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Zn}^{2+}$ for the ML and ML_2^- complexes, in the order $\text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$ for the $\text{M}(\text{OH})(\text{L})^-$ complexes with all the three ligands, and in the order, salicyloylglycine $>$ salicyloyl-dl- α -alanine $>$ salicyloyl dl-methionine for all the three metal ions. The results have been correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligands in the resulting complexes and compared with the corresponding values of the complexes formed by Cu^{2+} .

COMPLEXATION equilibria of transition metal ions with amino acids and small peptides have attracted considerable interest in recent years as many of these offer relatively simple models for the rather complex metalloenzymes¹⁻³. It is a general feature^{2,4} that protonation and metallation with a neutral amide group (CONH) occur at the amide carbonyl oxygen atom. Metallation at the amide nitrogen atom may occur only through substitution of the amide proton by the metal ion provided there is a primary ligating site on the ligand at a suitable position for chelate ring formation⁵. Salicyloyl derivatives of amino acids, viz. $(o)\text{HO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(=\text{O})\text{NHCH}(\text{R})\text{COOH}$ (hereafter H_sL), where $\text{R}=\text{H}$ (salicyloyl glycine or H_sSG), CH_3 (salicyloyl dl- α -alanine or H_sSA), $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SCH}_3$ (salicyloyl dl-methionine or H_sSM) have been found to provide bidentate ($\bar{\text{O}},\bar{\text{N}}$) chelation using the carboxylate oxygen atom and deprotonated amide nitrogen atom to Cu^{2+} leaving the phenolic hydroxyl groups uncoordinated to form both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 Cu^{2+} -ligand complexes of the types $\text{Cu}(\text{HL}-\text{H})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{HL}-\text{H})_2^{2-}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{L}-\text{H})(\text{HL}-\text{H})^{2-}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{L}-\text{H})_2^{4-}$ in the presence of an excess of the ligand (Cu^{2+} -ligand, 1 : 5 or 1 : 10)¹⁰⁻¹². In 1 : 1 Cu^{2+} -ligand mixtures, all these three ligands offered ($\bar{\text{O}},\bar{\text{N}},\bar{\text{O}}$) terdentate chelation to Cu^{2+} using phenolate oxygen, deprotonated amide nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen atoms to form the complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{L}-\text{H})(\text{H}_s\text{O})^{2-}$. The present paper describes the results of a pH-metric study on the complexation equilibria of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with these ligands.

Experimental

All the reagents were of AnalaR grade. Concentration of metal ions and of associated free acid (HNO_3) in the metal nitrate solutions were determined by combined ion-exchange, acidimetry and complexometric titrations¹⁴. Experimental procedure consisted of pH-metric titration of solutions containing known amount of the ligands (H_sL) containing a known amount of HNO_3 in the absence and in the presence of known amount of the metal ions with a standard NaOH solution at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (thermostated) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaNO_3) following the same procedure as described earlier¹⁰⁻¹². A Systronics 335 digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01) in conjunction with a special glass-electrode (pH 1-14) and a SCE was used for measuring pH. Representative pH-titration curves are shown in Fig 1. Stability constants were calculated by using the computer programme SCOGS¹⁵ at the Regional Computer Centre, Jadavpur University, Calcutta.

Results and Discussion

In the absence of metal ions all the ligands (H_sL) showed two well-separated buffer regions, pH 3-6 and 8-10 corresponding to successive deprotonation of COOH and OH (phenolic) groups. $\text{pK}_{\text{COOH}}^{\text{H}}$ and $\text{pK}_{\text{OH}}^{\text{H}}$ values evaluated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁶ are presented in Table 1.

Occurrence of carboxylic acid deprotonation equilibria of the ligands (H_sL) at the same pH

range both in the absence and in the presence of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions indicated non-involvement of carboxylate moiety in the complexation

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves of SGH_2 , SAH_2 , SMH_2 in absence and in presence of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3), $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.125 \text{ M}$, (initial volume = 25 ml): (1), 0.01 M HNO_3 ; (2), (1) + 0.001 M Ni^{2+} -nitrate; (3), (1) + 0.001 M Co^{2+} -nitrate; (4), (1) + 0.001 M Zn^{2+} -nitrate; (5), (1) + $0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SG}$; (6), (5) + 0.001 M Co^{2+} -nitrate; (7), (5) + 0.001 M Ni^{2+} -nitrate; (8), (5) + 0.001 M Zn^{2+} -nitrate; (9), (1) + $0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SA}$; (10), (9) + 0.01 M Co^{2+} -nitrate; (11), (9) + 0.001 M Ni^{2+} -nitrate; (12), (9) + 0.001 M Zn^{2+} -nitrate; (13), (1) + $0.001 \text{ M H}_2\text{SM}$; (14), (13) + 0.001 M Co^{2+} -nitrate; (15), (13) + 0.001 M Ni^{2+} -nitrate; and (16), (13) + 0.001 M Zn^{2+} -nitrate.

equilibria with these metal ions. However, the buffer region corresponding to the phenolic (OH) group deprotonation equilibria of the ligand anions (HL^-) in the presence of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions occurred at lower pH values (pH 6–9) than that in the absence of these ions. Two moles of base per mole of $\text{M}(\text{II})$ ions were consumed in this pH range. As the ligands were exclusively in the HL^- forms in the pH range of complexation with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions, the release of two protons per metal ion might be due to the formation of ML and ML_2^- complexes involving substitution of the phenolic proton of the HL^- ions by these metal ions (M^{2+}) according to equilibria (1) and (2),

Charges are dropped from the eqm. expressions for clarity. The possibility of bidentate (O,O) chelation of M^{2+} ions ($\text{M} = \text{Co}$, Ni and Zn) by the carbonyl oxygen atom of the amide moiety and the phenolate oxygen atom could not be ruled out. Bidentate (O,N) chelation by phenolate oxygen and deprotonated amide nitrogen leading to the formation of $\text{M}(\text{L}-\text{H})^-$ complexes involving the release of two protons per metal ion according to eqm. (3),

as a result of substitution of the phenolic proton and the amide proton was unlikely to occur in the presence of large excess of the ligand in these systems.

Now as the pH range of metal-ligand complexation equilibria and the hydrolytic equilibria of the M^{2+} (aq.) ions were quite close, the possibility of formation of hydroxo complexes could not be ruled out. The preliminary values of the constants K_{ML}^M

TABLE 1 - PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS* WITH SGH_2 , SAH_2 AND SMH_2
Medium: 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3), Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

H_2L		$\text{M}(\text{II})$	$\log K_{\text{M(L)}}^M$	$\log K_{\text{M(L)}_2}^{\text{M(L)}}$	$\log K_{\text{(M+L+H}_2\text{O)}}^{\text{H}}$	$\log K_{\text{M(OH)(L)}}^{\text{M}}$	$\Delta \log K_M$
$\text{pK}_{\text{COOH}}^{\text{H}}$	$\text{pK}_{\text{OH}}^{\text{H}}$						
4.00	H_2SG	Co	3.13	3.98	-4.19	9.81	0.04
		Ni	3.36	3.15	-4.35	9.65	0.11
		Zn	4.12	3.86	-5.33	8.67	-2.01
4.22	H_2SA	Co	3.07	2.92	-4.23	9.77	0.06
		Ni	3.17	3.04	-4.51	9.49	-0.06
		Zn	3.96	3.75	-5.48	8.52	-2.00
4.05	H_2SM	Co	2.92	2.69	-4.37	9.63	0.07
		Ni	3.06	2.85	-4.59	9.41	-0.03
		Zn	3.76	3.50	-5.66	8.34	-1.98

$\text{pK}_{\text{M}}^{\text{H}} = 7.36(\text{Co}), 7.62(\text{Ni}), 7.44(\text{Zn})$; $\text{pK}_{\text{M}}^{\text{OH}} = 15.51(\text{Co}), 15.88(\text{Ni}), 16.42(\text{Zn})$; $\text{pK}_{\text{H}} = 14.00$ at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

*Limits of error in the constants: $\pm 0.02 \sim \pm 0.04$ in log units.

and K_{ML}^M evaluated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁶ were, therefore, subjected to computational refinement using the computer programme SCIGS¹⁵ considering the equilibria (4), (5) and (6),

to occur simultaneously with the complexation equilibria (1) and (2). Preliminary value of the overall formation constant of $M(OH)(L)^-$ complexes were computed with the equilibria (7) and (8),

The constants $\Delta \log K_M$ and $\log K_{M^{2+}+HL+H_2O}^H$ could be related to the binary constants K_M^H and K_{ML}^M by relation (9),

$$\Delta \log K_M = \log K_{(M+L+H_2O)}^H - \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_M^H \quad (9)$$

Preliminary estimates of $\log K_{(M+L+H_2O)}^H$ could be obtained from eqm. (9) by using the experimentally determined values of $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_M^H$ and statistically calculated values of $\Delta \log K_M^{17,18}$. The overall stability constant $K_{M(OH)(L)}^H$ of the complex $M(OH)(L)^-$ could be calculated with the aid of relation (10),

$$\log K_{M(OH)(L)}^H = \log K_{(M+L+H_2O)}^H + pK_w \quad (10)$$

where, K_w stands for ionic product of water at experimental temperature¹⁹.

The species LH^- , L^{2-} , M^{2+} , $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(L)$, $M(L)_2^{2-}$ and $M(OH)(L)^-$ were, therefore, considered to exist in the complexation equilibria in calculating the formation constants using the

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of $Co^{2+} - H_2SG$ system: (C1) HSG^- , (C2) $Co(OH)^+$, (C3) $Co(OH)_2$; (C4) $Co(SG)$, (C5) $Co(SG)_2^{2-}$, (C6) $Co(OH)(SG)^-$, (FM) Co^{2+} and (FL) SG^{2-} .

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of $Ni^{2+} - H_2SG$ system: (C1) HSG^- , (C2) $Ni(OH)^+$, (C3) $Ni(OH)_2$, (C4) $Ni(SG)$, (C5) $Ni(SG)_2^{2-}$, (C6) $Ni(OH)(SG)^-$, (FM) Ni^{2+} and (FL) SG^{2-} .

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves of $Zn^{2+} - H_2SG$ system: (C1) HSG^- , (C2) $Zn(OH)^+$, (C3) $Zn(OH)_2$, (C4) $Zn(SG)$, (C5) $Zn(SG)_2^{2-}$, (C6) $Zn(OH)(SG)^-$, (FM) Zn^{2+} and (FL) SG^{2-} .

computer programme SCIGS¹⁵. The constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the refined values (Table 1) were used to calculate the representative species distribution curves (Figs. 2-4).

Stability of ML and ML_2^{2-} complexes are found to be in the order, $Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} < Zn^{2+}$ for all the three ligands, and in the order, $SGH_2 > SAH_2 > SMH_2$ for all the three metal ions in spite of the basicity order, $SAH^- > SGH^- > SMH^-$ of the ligand (HL^-) ions. Steric effects by the CH_3 group in SA^{2-} and $CH_3CH_2SCH_3$ group in SM^{2-} are possibly responsible for lower stability of the complexes formed by these ligands as compared to those of the analogous complexes formed by the ligand SG^{2-} ions. Comparable stability of complexes formed by a particular metal ion with all the three ligands suggest identical mode of bonding by SG^{2-} , SA^{2-} and SM^{2-} ions in spite of the fact that SM^{2-} has an extra binding site, viz. SCH_3 group of the methionine side chain which, therefore, remains uncoordinated in the metal complexes derived from SM^{2-} . Similar conclusion was also arrived at for the complexes of Cu^{2+} with these

ligands²¹. Stability of ternary $M(OH)(L)^-$ complexes are in the order, $Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$. Small positive or small negative $\Delta \log K_M$ values for the Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes suggest favourable formation of ternary $M(OH)(L)^-$ complexes with these two metal ions, obviously due to $M \cdots \rightarrow O \cdots C \cdots NH$ π -bonding, a factor that is absent with Zn^{2+} and consequently the ternary $Zn(OH)(L)^-$ complexes are less favoured as is indicated by large negative values of $\Delta \log K_{Zn}$ as compared to $\Delta \log K_{Co}$ and $\Delta \log K_{Ni}$.

In the presence of Cu^{2+} the carboxylic acid deprotonation equilibria of the ligands occurred at lower pH than that in the absence of Cu^{2+} while phenolic (OH) deprotonation equilibria occurred at the same pH range both in the presence and in the absence of Cu^{2+} because the ligands offered bidentate (N, O) chelation using the carboxylate oxygen and deprotonated amide nitrogen atoms to form the complexes $Cu(HL-H)$ and $Cu(HL-H)_2^{2-}$ having uncoordinated phenolic hydroxyl groups. Therefore, the complexation equilibria of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with these ligands are quite different from those of Cu^{2+} .

Species distribution curves (Figs. 2, 3) show that M^{2+} , $M(OH)^+$ and $M(OH)(L)^-$ are the major metal containing species with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in the region of biological pH, where the higher complexes $M(OH)_2$, ML_2^{2-} contribute but very little. With Zn^{2+} however (Fig. 4) the predominant metal containing species in the region of biological pH are Zn^{2+} , ZnL and ZnL_2^{2-} complexes, hydroxo species $Zn(OH)^+$, $Zn(OH)_2$ and $Zn(OH)(L)^-$ are formed in negligibly small amounts only.

This model study thus shows the ligand preference of Zn^{2+} in peptide complexes is somewhat

different from that of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . This might be of some relevance to the nature's selection of Zn^{2+} in preference to Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} as the co-factor in many enzymatic reactions.

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